

Loud Bicycle Pre-selection Report.

Abstract

In this paper, the optimization of sound emission from a bicycle wheel mechanism is investigated by modeling a thin plate as a collection of parallel rods. This discrete representation enables an in-depth analysis of the rods' responses to repeated impacts with the wheel spokes and facilitates maximizing sound output while preserving the bicycle's functionality. Two experimental setups were employed, using specialized sensors for precise measurements and improved acoustic understanding. Simple modifications to the classic card trick and the choice of suitable materials demonstrated that significantly louder sounds could be achieved.

1 Introduction

The plate is modeled as a collection of parallel rods. The focus of this study is placed on the case where the plate is symmetrically struck relative to its fixed edge. Under such conditions, the repeated impacts with the wheel spokes are interpreted as point forces exerted on each rod.

The bending of each rod under the applied force, their transverse oscillations, and the acoustic waves generated by these vibrations are analyzed. The behavior of each rod is modeled using the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory (1). The strength of this model is found in its ability to accurately describe the bending of slender beams under small deflections, where shear deformations and rotational inertia are neglected.

This simplification provides a manageable framework that remains analytically solvable even with the inclusion of additional damping terms, which are critical for this study.

2 Theoretical Model

To begin with, the problem is formulated by partitioning the plate into M rods of length L with N points each and width S/M . The point where the rod is first struck by the spoke is denoted as \tilde{x}_0 , and subsequently, it is rolled over at the next points \tilde{x}_i until it is slipped off the card at $\tilde{x}_N = L$. Since $\tilde{x}_k = \tilde{x}_{k-1} + \Delta x \Rightarrow \tilde{x}_k = \frac{k(L-\tilde{x}_0)}{N} + \tilde{x}_0$.

Figure 1: Mathematical formulation of a card struck by a spoke.

The partial differential equation describing the transverse vibration of a uniform elastic homogeneous isotropic Euler-Bernoulli beam is formulated in terms of EI , μ , r_a , and r_i , which represent the flexural rigidity of the beam, the mass per unit length of the beam, the coefficient of external damping of the beam, and the coefficient of internal damping of the beam (Kelvin-Voigt), respectively. The

deflection of the beam at point x and time t is denoted by $u(x, t)$, while the load per unit length of the beam at point x and time t is denoted by $F(x, t)$ (1).

$$EI \frac{\partial^4 u(x, t)}{\partial x^4} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial t^2} + r_e \frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial t} + r_i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial^4 u(x, t)}{\partial x^4} \right) = F(x, t) \quad (1)$$

The force exerted by the spoke is modeled as a linear force that depends on the initial point of impact and the relative velocity between the spoke and the beam. This force is experimentally measured using piezoelectric sensors placed at different locations, and an empirical formula is derived based on these measurements. The force can be determined if its value is known at two points, which can be achieved for the boundary points as

$$F(\tilde{x}_0) \sim \mu L \frac{\omega R - \frac{\partial u(\tilde{x}_0, t_0 + kT_a)}{\partial t}}{t_k - t_{k+1}}, \quad F(L) \sim \frac{2IE \cos \theta_0}{\tilde{x}_0^2} \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the following equation for the force is derived, as shown in Figures 2,3.

$$F(\tilde{x}_\xi) = A\tilde{x}_\xi + B = \frac{F(L) - F(\tilde{x}_0)}{L - \tilde{x}_0} \tilde{x}_\xi + \frac{F(\tilde{x}_0) \cdot L - \tilde{x}_0 \cdot F(L)}{L - \tilde{x}_0} \quad (3)$$

It is expected that the force generally changes over each period. However, for a sufficiently large number of impacts, due to the exponential behavior of the damping, the memory of previous oscillations is lost by the system, and eventually, the force is approximated to be the same. This is why a consistent sound is heard for each impact.

Figure 2: The force applied to the rod by the spoke when it is initially at rest and after multiple impacts.

Hence, the force is described as a moving load that travels along the beam, where \tilde{x}_ξ represents each point the spoke passes at time t_ξ .

The relationship between the two is expressed as $\tilde{x}_\xi \approx \frac{L^2 - \tilde{x}_0^2}{R\omega} \cdot t_\xi$. The period of the repeated strikes up to that moment is denoted as $T_a = \frac{2\pi R}{v_{\text{bicycle}} \times (\text{spokes})}$, where R (maximum 33 cm) is the distance at which the card is placed, and spokes represents the number of spokes in the bike, typically ranging from 24 to 36.

$$F(x, t) = F(x)\delta(x - vt) \approx \sum_{k=0}^K \sum_{\xi=0}^{\Xi} F(\tilde{x}_\xi)\delta(x - \tilde{x}_\xi)\delta(t - (t_\xi + k \cdot T_a)) \quad (4)$$

Experimental data for four different spoke strike scenarios were collected for the optimally dimensioned aluminum plate (gray square with partitioning), along with the corresponding fitted lines, which were plotted. In the first case, the spoke strikes the stationary plate just once (Black), while in the second case, the spoke strikes while in motion (Red) after repeated impacts, resulting in relative velocity between the plate and spoke. In the last two cases, magnets were added to the setup, attracted by an external magnet above the plate, which increases the plate's resistance to the spoke impact and applies a restoring force to return the plate to its equilibrium position, further increasing the relative velocity between the spoke and plate. Additionally, the characteristic resistance R and force f curve for the force sensor is presented in the graph, following $f \sim R^{-1}$, as derived from the instrument's data sheet. Some representative measurements used for the calibration of the piezoelectric sensor, taking into account the dimensions, are provided in the additional materials of the paper.

Figure 3. Data collected from specific points on the partitioning of the plate and are used for a more precise linear fit, following the equation (3). The force sensors were calibrated using known masses, and the values obtained were used to validate the theoretical calculations.

The method of separation of variables is applied to the homogeneous problem (1)

$$\frac{x^{(IV)}}{x} = -\frac{\mu \ddot{T} + r_a \dot{T}}{EIT + r_i \dot{T}} = \left(\frac{\gamma}{L}\right)^4 = k^4 \quad (5)$$

And after applying the boundary conditions for a clamped end ($x = 0$) and a free end ($x = L$), respectively (1)

$$\begin{aligned} u(0, t) = 0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial u(x, t)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=0} &= 0, \\ \left. \frac{\partial^2 u(x, t)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=L} = 0, \quad \left. \frac{\partial^3 u(x, t)}{\partial x^3} \right|_{x=L} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The transcendental eigenvalue equation is obtained as

$$\cos(\gamma_n) \cosh(\gamma_n) + 1 = 0 \quad (7)$$

The eigenfunctions of the free vibrations are given as (1)

$$\begin{aligned} X_n(x) = & (\sin(\gamma_n) + \sinh(\gamma_n)) \cdot (\cos(\gamma_n x/L) - \cosh(\gamma_n x/L)) \\ & + (\cos(\gamma_n) + \cosh(\gamma_n)) \cdot (\sinh(\gamma_n x/L) - \sin(\gamma_n x/L)) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

For the non-homogeneous problem, the method of modal analysis is applied.

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{L} \left\{ \sum_n X_n(x) T_n(t) \right\} = F(x, t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} F_n(t) X_n(x) = \\ \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\int_0^L F(x, t) X_n(x, t) dx}{\int_0^L X_n(x, t)^2 dx} X_n(x) = \\ \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{j=0}^K \sum_{\xi=0}^{\Xi} \frac{X_n(\tilde{x}_\xi) F(\tilde{x}_\xi) \delta(t - (t_\xi + j \cdot T_a)) X_n(x)}{\int_0^L X_n^2(x) dx}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

From this, a second-order non-homogeneous ordinary differential equation with constant coefficients is obtained.

$$\ddot{T}_n(t) + \left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{\mu} \right) \dot{T}_n(t) + \left(\frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu} \right) T_n(t) = F_n(t). \quad (10)$$

The rod is assumed to be initially at rest; therefore, the solution obtained through various methods, such as the Laplace transform, is given as (Appendix C)

$$T_n(t) = \begin{cases} \int_0^t F_n(t - \tau) e^{-\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \tau} \sin \left(\sqrt{\frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu} - \left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \right)^2} \tau \right) d\tau, & \text{if } \frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu} - \left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \right)^2 > 0, \\ \int_0^t F_n(t - \tau) \tau e^{-\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \tau} d\tau, & \text{if } \frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu} - \left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \right)^2 = 0, \\ \int_0^t F_n(t - \tau) e^{-\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \tau} \sinh \left(\sqrt{\left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \right)^2 - \frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu}} \tau \right) d\tau, & \text{if } \left(\frac{r_e + k_n^4 r_i}{2\mu} \right)^2 - \frac{k_n^4 EI}{\mu} > 0. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The final equation for the transverse vibrations of the rod is given by

equally spaced point sources at intervals Δz , the pressure at a point \vec{r} is given by the sum of the monopole contributions. Where c_0 is the speed of sound in air and τ the time delay between neighboring monopoles. (3)

$$\begin{aligned} P(r, \omega) &= \sum_{n=-N}^N \frac{Q}{4\pi r_n} e^{-ikr_n - i\omega t} \\ &= \sum_{n=-N}^N \frac{Q}{4\pi r} e^{-ikr} e^{ink(\Delta z \cos \theta - \tau/c_0)} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

For the card, the contribution from multiple rods is considered. The pressure for a specific vibration mode ω_n at a distance \vec{r} from the origin is given by the double summation. (3):

$$\begin{aligned} P(r, \omega_n) &= \sum_{l=0}^N \sum_{m=0}^M \frac{Q_{ln}}{4\pi} e^{-ilk_n \tau_{lm}/c_0} \frac{e^{-ik_n(r_{0m} + l \cdot \cos \theta_m \cdot \Delta z)}}{r_{0m}} \\ &\approx M \cdot \sum_{l=0}^N \frac{Q_{ln}}{4\pi r} e^{-ik_n(r - l \cdot \cos \theta \cdot \Delta z)} \approx M \cdot \sum_{l=0}^N \frac{Q_{ln}}{4\pi r} e^{-ik_n r} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Where the source flux amplitude is given by (3)

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{ln} &= \langle 4\pi \cdot u_n^2(l \cdot (\Delta z), t) \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial t}(l \cdot (\Delta z), t) \rangle_t \\ &= \frac{1}{T_a} \int_t^{t+kT_a} 4\pi \cdot u_n^2(l \cdot (\Delta z), t) \frac{\partial u_n}{\partial t}(l \cdot (\Delta z), t) dt \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

The sound intensity that we perceive is represented by the Sound Pressure Level (SPL). It is a logarithmic measure of the sound pressure relative to a reference value, typically used to quantify the perceived intensity of sound. SPL is expressed in decibels (dB) and indicates how much the sound pressure deviates from the reference sound pressure level. The reference sound pressure p_{ref} is typically 20×10^{-6} Pa in air, which corresponds to the threshold of human hearing (3).

$$L_p(r, \theta) = 10 \log \left(\frac{\langle |p^2(r, \theta, t)| \rangle_t}{p_{\text{ref}}^2} \right) \quad (17)$$

The Sound Pressure Level (SPL) is measured using the Root Mean Square (RMS) of the sound pressure (3).

$$\langle P(r, \omega_n) \rangle_{RMS} = \left(\frac{1}{N+M} \sum_{l=0}^N \sum_{m=0}^M P(r, \omega_n)^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (18)$$

The human ear does not respond equally to all frequencies. Humans can typically hear sounds within the range of 20 Hz to 20 kHz, with the most impactful frequencies for the human ear lying between 500 Hz and 6 kHz. To account for the varying sensitivity of the ear at different sound levels, two weighting filters are commonly used: A-weighting, which is applied for low to moderate sound levels and C-weighting, which is used for high sound levels and provides a nearly flat frequency response to capture more low-frequency content. For reference, the A-weighting curve is given below (3):

$$R_A(f) = \frac{12194^2 f^4}{(f^2 + 20.6^2) \sqrt{(f^2 + 107.7^2)(f^2 + 737.9^2)} (f^2 + 12194^2)} \quad (19)$$

The Sound Pressure Level (SPL) sums logarithmically; hence, for different modes within the frequency range that the human ear can respond to, the final formula is obtained as (3):

$$L_p(\vec{r}) = 10 \log_{10} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{eff}} 10^{(L_p(r, \omega_n) + R_A(f_n))/10} \text{ (dBA)} \quad (20)$$

For the optimization of sound intensity, it is necessary to maximize the amplitude and oscillation velocity at the most impactful frequencies to ensure optimal energy transfer. Assuming that $\mathbf{a} = (E, L, S, \mu, r_e, r_i, A, B, \tilde{x}_0)$, the argument is defined as a vector that encompasses the parameters influencing the oscillation amplitude and velocity. An optimization method is applied for variables within finite intervals, utilizing the steepest descent approach to minimize the function $F(\mathbf{a}) = -\langle u(x, t) \rangle_{T_a, L} = -\frac{1}{L \cdot T_a} \int_0^L \int_k^{(k+1) T_a} \nabla_{\mathbf{a}} u(x, t; \mathbf{a}) dt dx$ for the frequencies between 1000 Hz and 5000 Hz, where A-weighting contributes a positive value. A small step size γ needs to be chosen, as the Barzilai-Borwein method is not applicable in this case (Appendix C).

$$\mathbf{a}_{n+1} = \mathbf{a}_n + \gamma \cdot \frac{1}{L \cdot T_a} \int_0^L \int_k^{(k+1) T_a} \nabla_{\mathbf{a}} u(x, t; \mathbf{a}) dt dx \quad (21)$$

A reference is made to the additional sound source generated by the vibrations of the spokes. The vibrations of the spoke striking the card can be modeled as an external force $F(x, t) \sim (H(x) - H(x - S))$, altering the spectral equation to: $\cosh(\lambda L) \cdot \cos(\lambda L) = 1$. Computationally, the resulting sound intensity corrections (1 – 5dB) are within the measurement error and approximations, making them negligible. Validation comes from rigid materials with high damping, like thick cardboard, which produce low-intensity sound despite significant impacts. This behavior is attributed to the spoke's clamped boundary conditions and material properties, which limit vibration amplitudes at key frequencies. Further discussion on this topic is provided in Appendix B.

3 Experimental Confirmation

In order to study the problem, two different setups are designed. One consists of a wheel (32 spokes, 30cm radius) resembling that of a bicycle, while the other includes a motor with adjustable speed that strikes the card, aiming to study how a spoke interacts with the card. The card is placed as externally as possible for better accuracy of the model. The sound meter is placed at the maximum possible distance (usually 7 meters) to ensure an accurate approximation of the far field. Additionally, in the second setup, the sound meter is calibrated to the motor's noise at 50 dB and operates with A-weighting. All measurements have an error margin of ± 5 dB. (video provided in the additional files).

Figure 7a: Configuration using a bicycle wheel for regular motion, with the sound meter positioned at a distance. **Figure 7b:** Motor setup featuring a spoke-like metallic beam for more precise movement control.

Figure 8a: Flex sensor placed in the setup, measuring the angle of the tip relative to the axis perpendicular to the plane at its base. **Figure 8b:** Three types of sensors: Flex sensor, piezo sensor, and force sensor. **Figure 8c:** Piezo sensors, using a force threshold to record signals, provide an initial idea of the forces on the card from the spoke, without involving the movement of the force sensor. **Figure 8d:** Triple Axis Gyroscope and Accelerometer used for velocity measurement with maximum possible accuracy. **Figures 8e, 8f:** High-precision force sensor for both low and high forces. Depending on its position on the rod relative to the point of first contact, it can measure the corresponding force effectively.

For the experiment, the speed of the bicycle is maintained at 15 ± 2 km/h, which is considered a typical speed for a bicycle on flat terrain, ridden by an amateur cyclist. At any given time, the speed of the wheel was measured using a speedometer or a gyroscope/3-axis accelerometer.

To obtain a frequency and SPL graph, it is necessary to know the sensitivity of the microphone. A dynamic cardioid microphone with a frequency response below 18 kHz is used; therefore, values above this range are not considered. The room's baseline noise level is set at 30 dB, and sounds below this threshold are disregarded.

Different card materials were used, featuring various geometries and combinations. Overall, no noticeable acoustic difference related to the shape of the card was observed. Cards with larger edges tended to get caught in the spokes, while edge modifications did not significantly affect the timbre of the sound. The only notable observation was that, among plastic (PET), hard paper (HP), and aluminum (Al), aluminum produced the loudest sound.

In order to optimize the setup, efforts were made to increase the speed of the card as it passed through the equilibrium point by

adding springs or magnets to the arrangement, and a measurable contribution was observed. Additionally, a horn was added to minimize acoustic losses. Even a simple plastic bottle was shown to contribute a few decibels to the final measurement.

Figure 9a: Plastic cylinder used to enhance sound, functioning as a horn. **Figure 9b:** Custom-designed horn, respecting the dimensions of the most influential wavelengths. **Figure 9c:** Springs that amplify the force between the spoke and the card, synchronizing their impacts to achieve maximum relative speed. **Figure 9d:** Similar setup with magnets, studied in more detail compared to the springs. Theoretical analysis was also conducted with the help of Figure 3.

Figure 10: Histogram of experimental recordings for the frequencies (blue), corresponding to an aluminum card with dimensions 14×8 cm. The theory is applied to two different force scenarios: (1) with the correction for relative velocity in the applied force (black line) and (2) without this correction (red line). Some characteristic harmonics for the material are shown in the graph. Between 4,000 and 6,000 Hz, we observe the most impactful frequencies, which is why the sound is stronger in this range, as shown in the inset graph. The shaded areas indicate regions where frequencies are less impactful for human hearing. Additionally, a lower threshold for intensity has been set at 30 dB, as measurements below this level are meaningless due to the microphone's sensitivity.

Figure 11: Experimental comparison between three different configurations: two materials, hard paper (HP) and plastic (PET), both of which have significantly lower Young’s modulus compared to aluminum (Al). Additionally, a horn is incorporated into the setup as a waveguide to enhance sound projection. Large oscillation amplitudes are observed at higher frequencies, which are less impactful.

Noticeable additional noise production is observed when external parts are used. In some cases the observed difference remains within the margin of error, making it uncertain whether the setup contributes significantly, for instance when springs are used instead of magnets, likely because the setup creates constraints on the plate, affecting its dynamics. The horn achieves consistently an increase in SPL, as expected due to improved impedance matching between the sound source and air. This makes the horn the most effective means for producing a noticeably louder sound. This also alters the card’s timbre, causing a significant deviation from the theoretical predictions in this case.

Figure 12: Magnets are attached to the Al-card. The final SPL value in C-weighting is also provided. For the theoretical study, the fitted lines from Fig. 3 were used.

To illustrate the contribution of each parameter to the phenomenon, a radar chart is plotted for the key factors. The most compatible results provided by the gradient descent algorithm are also plotted alongside. The internal damping, modeled by the Kelvin–Voigt mechanism, is ignored in this case, as it is negligible for solids (1).

Figure 13: Radar Chart of $\mathbf{a} = (E, L, S, \mu, r_e, A, \bar{x}_0)$. The variables were normalized to their respective value ranges. It appears that all parameters play a role to some extent in maximizing the intensity, with the most decisive factor being the force between the rod and the card, which is determined by (Young’s modulus), the mass, and the dimensions of the card.

The experimental setup achieving maximum sound was characterized by an aluminum plate with a thickness of 48 mm and dimensions of $L \times S = 14 \times 8 \text{ cm}$. The plate, which was square and had a Young’s modulus of 65.39GPa, was positioned so that the first contact point between the spoke and the plate was 8.5cm from the clamped edge. It was experimentally confirmed that the sound can be further enhanced by incorporating additional components into the setup, such as magnets or springs that reinforce the plate’s return to its equilibrium position, as well as a horn that better directs the sound. The study of these additional components is considered within the scope of the problem, as similar elements are commonly employed in the toy market and in DIY projects. Many manufacturers utilize such components to amplify the sound or to achieve different timbres, aiming to better mimic various types of vehicles.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

The theoretical model, developed using the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory, can adequately study the vibration of the card. Additionally, the discretization into elementary acoustic sources provides a reasonably accurate approximation of the sound intensity. The experimental setup is capable of mapping the sound and distinguishing significant changes in both the spectrum and the sound intensity. It is indicated that while all parameters influence the final SPL, increased damping and flexural rigidity synchronized with the period T_a lead to stronger impacts and, consequently, louder sound. Therefore, it was demonstrated that a thin aluminum card, simple magnets, and a plastic bottle could be used to enhance the sound of a bicycle and adjust it to match the desired timbre of the intended vehicle (for a better imitation of a motorcycle).

In the future, the theory aims to be extended to other beam theories, improved approaches to damping terms proportional to $\sim u''(x, t)$ and the cantilever plate, which is governed by a more complex nonlinear equation (4)

$$\nabla^4 w(x, y, t) + \frac{\rho h}{D} \frac{\partial^2 w(x, y, t)}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (22)$$

Also, further investigation can be conducted using the slip-and-stick phenomenon for a more qualitative and concise analysis (see Appendix A). It is also of interest to explore how such an approach can be applied to more complex systems.

Regarding the setup, it is aimed to be studied with greater accuracy by incorporating higher-precision piezoelectric sensors and conducting measurements in an external environment, free from the wall-induced reverberations of a room. Additionally, some movements of the rod were simulated in MATLAB and are presented as videos in the additional documents as well.

Finally, a computational simulation of the acoustic wave is being developed using the FDTD method. Simulations were performed in MATLAB using an adapted version of the Yee algorithm. Some initial examples are presented (video FDTD provided in the additional files). However, the current stage remains qualitative, providing a representation of the wave propagation for a specific mode of the plate.

References

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5 Appendix

5.1 Appendix A - Slip and Stick

The slip-and-stick phenomenon (2) can be used to simulate the vibrations at the edge of the plate. A mathematical description of such a phenomenon is provided below for a more concise and qualitative understanding of the process. For L_0 initial sticking position. The equation of motion for the tip of the card is given by (2):

$$0 = F - T(\dot{L}_0) \quad (23)$$

For a linear range of spring strains (2):

$$m\ddot{L} = F - T(\dot{L}_0 + \dot{L}) - kL \quad (24)$$

Assuming that $T(\dot{L}_0 + \dot{L})$ can be expanded into a Taylor series around the speed of $\dot{x}_0(2)$:

$$T(\dot{L}_0 + \dot{L}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{L^n}{n!} \frac{d^n T(\dot{L}_0 + \dot{L})}{d\dot{L}_0^n} \quad (25)$$

For low value of \dot{L} or slow changes of the friction force as a function of velocity, the summation can be truncated after the first three terms (2):

$$T(\dot{L}_0 + \dot{L}) \approx T(\dot{L}_0) + \dot{L} \frac{dT}{d\dot{L}_0} + \frac{\dot{L}^2}{2!} \frac{d^2 T}{d\dot{L}_0^2} \quad (26)$$

The expansion is introduced into the equation (2):

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{L} + \frac{dT}{d\dot{L}_0} \dot{L} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 T}{d\dot{L}_0^2} \dot{L}^2 + kL &= 0 \\ \Rightarrow \ddot{L} + 2b\dot{L} + aL^2 + \omega_0^2 L &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

In which

$$2b = \frac{1}{m} \frac{dT}{d\dot{L}_0}, \quad a = \frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2 T}{d\dot{L}_0^2}, \quad \omega_0^2 = \frac{k}{m}$$

The solution of the equation has two constants r, φ for given initial conditions, $\omega^2 = \omega_0^2 - b^2 > 0$

$$\begin{aligned} L = & -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\omega_0^2}{b^2} ar^2 e^{-2bt} + 2re^{-bt} \cos(\omega t + \varphi) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} ar^2 e^{-2bt} \cos(2\omega t + 2\varphi) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

5.2 Appendix B - Vibrations of the Spoke

The vibrations of the spoke, as it strikes the rod, can also be taken into account. The only significant difference is that the force now becomes a difference of Heaviside functions in the dimensions of the plate, while the solutions of the eigenfunctions are slightly altered due to the fixed ends. The spectral equations now become (1):

$$\cosh(\lambda L) \cdot \cos(\lambda L) = 1 \quad (29)$$

For an external force $F(x, t) \sim (H(x) - H(x - S))$. What is observed computationally is that the difference in the sound intensity produced by the spoke leads to corrections on the order of 1-5 dB, which are very close to the measurement error of the instrumentation and the approximations made. Therefore, it does not make

sense to take it into account. This can also be verified by using rigid materials with high internal damping, such as thick cardboard. In such cases, the sound produced is of very low intensity; however, the impact on the spoke remains significant and sufficient to induce vibrations, but exhibit negligible amplitudes at the most influential frequencies. This is primarily attributed to the clamped boundary conditions of the spoke and its material properties.

5.3 Appendix C - Supplementary Calculations

The inner product of the eigenfunctions is given by:

$$\int_0^L X_n^2(x) dx = \frac{Le^{-2\gamma n}}{2\gamma n} ((\sinh \gamma n + \sin \gamma n)^2 \cdot (e^{2\gamma n} (\cos(2\gamma n) + 2\gamma n - 4e^{\gamma n} \sin \gamma n - 1))) \quad (30)$$

Where the eigenfunctions $X_n(x)$ are orthogonal such that

$$\int_0^L X_i(x)X_j(x)dx = \delta_{ij} \cdot \int_0^L X_i(x)X_i(x)dx \quad (31)$$

For an operator \hat{L}_n such that

$$\begin{aligned} L(u) = A_0 u + A_1 \frac{du}{dt} + A_2 \frac{d^2 u}{dt^2} + \dots \\ + A_{n-1} \frac{d^{n-1} u}{dt^{n-1}} + \frac{d^n u}{dt^n} = f(t) \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Subject to the initial conditions

$$u(0) = \frac{du(0)}{dt} = \dots = \frac{d^{n-1} u(0)}{dt^{n-1}} = 0 \quad (33)$$

The problem's solution is given by

$$u(t) = \int_0^t U(t-\tau) f(\tau) d\tau \quad (34)$$

Where $L(U) = 0$ represents the solution to the homogeneous problem.

Regarding optimization, we first differentiate the function and then apply a numerical integration rule for each element of the vector.

$$\int_0^L \int_{kT_a}^{(k+1)T_a} \nabla_a u(x, t; \mathbf{a}) dt dx \approx \sum_{x_i} \sum_{t_j} \nabla_a u(x_i, t_j; \mathbf{a}) \Delta t \Delta x \quad (35)$$

The process is repeated iteratively. If it becomes computationally expensive, a subset of the parameters is selected for investigation, and the procedure is repeated for all subsets.

$$\mathbf{a}_{n+1} = \mathbf{a}_n + \gamma \cdot \frac{1}{L \cdot T_a} \sum_{x_i} \sum_{t_j} \nabla_a u(x_i, t_j; \mathbf{a}) \Delta t \Delta x \quad (36)$$

In this way, the optimal elements of the vector are determined.

5.4 Appendix D - Multiple Cards

If multiple cards are attached to a wheel, it is equivalent to having several sources, represented by the number v . Since acoustic sources combine logarithmically, the total source will effectively be:

$$L_{v-cards} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(10^{\frac{L_1}{10}} + 10^{\frac{L_2}{10}} + \dots + 10^{\frac{L_v}{10}} \right) \quad (37)$$

The cards contribute equally acoustically, as they are identical and the far-field approximations apply. Therefore, it will hold that $L_1 = L_2 = \dots = L_v = L$, and thus, we calculate...

$$L_{v-cards} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} \left(v \cdot 10^{\frac{L}{10}} \right) = 10 \cdot \log_{10} (v) + L \quad (38)$$

Based on the arrangement we have developed, each card is always placed at the outermost point of its respective spoke. Therefore, the maximum number of cards that can be placed on the bicycle, contributing to optimal intensity, will be at most equal to the number of spokes $v \leq \text{number of spokes}$. Therefore, for a wheel with 32 spokes, for example, the maximum theoretical contribution would be,

$$L_{v-cards} = 10 \cdot \log_{10} (v) + L \leq L + 15dB \quad (39)$$

That is, at most, an additional 15dB beyond the original source. However, in practice, even 10 cards are sufficient to observe a 10dB increase, which cannot be attributed to instrument error. Indeed, this is recorded on the sound meter of our setup when testing with 10 cards, although it makes the arrangement less user-friendly. It is ultimately up to the individual cyclist to decide how to maximize the sound intensity. Nevertheless, a simpler setup using magnets or a horn could achieve similar results while having less impact on the bicycle's functionality.

6 Additional Data

A table is presented detailing the calibration process for the piezoelectric sensors. The relationship between resistance and force is given by $f \sim R^{-1}$, where f represents the force and R denotes the resistance, as derived from the instrument's provided data sheet. Based on this calibration, we were able to calculate the force for each individual case. These additions offer a comprehensive overview of the experimental procedure and data, ensuring that readers can replicate and fully understand the methodology. We trust this enhances both the clarity and robustness of our study.

Force (N)	Resistance (Ω)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)
1	100000	4.545	0.00001
2	50500	4.174	0.00008
3	34000	3.864	0.00011
4	25750	3.601	0.00014
5	20800	3.377	0.00016
6	17500	3.182	0.00018
7	15142	3.011	0.00020
8	13375	2.861	0.00021
9	12000	2.727	0.00023
10	10900	2.608	0.00024

A table summarizing the angles measured for different applied forces, which were used to calculate the Young's modulus for the tested materials. The relationship between the force and the observed deformation is analyzed according to the formula:

$$l = \sqrt{\frac{IE}{2f}} \int_{\theta}^{\pi/2} \frac{d\theta}{\sqrt{\cos\theta_0 - \cos\theta}}$$

We present the table containing the data obtained for each material.

Index	θ_0 (degrees)	θ_0 (radians)	Force (N)	E (GPa)
0	5	0.087266	0.021	1.442
1	10	0.174533	0.024	1.572
2	15	0.261799	0.023	1.471
3	20	0.349066	0.024	1.514
4	25	0.436332	0.023	1.427
5	30	0.523599	0.025	1.438
6	35	0.610865	0.028	1.568
7	40	0.698132	0.028	1.427
8	45	0.785398	0.032	1.517
9	50	0.872665	0.036	1.549
10	55	0.959931	0.040	1.529
11	60	1.047198	0.044	1.487
12	65	1.134464	0.051	1.443
13	70	1.221730	0.064	1.467
14	75	1.308997	0.089	1.557
15	80	1.396263	0.130	1.519
16	85	1.483530	0.246	1.445
17	5	0.087266	0.052	3.491
18	10	0.174533	0.054	3.588
19	15	0.261799	0.055	3.615
20	20	0.349066	0.058	3.650
21	25	0.436332	0.060	3.688
22	30	0.523599	0.059	3.475
23	35	0.610865	0.061	3.395
24	40	0.698132	0.071	3.672
25	45	0.785398	0.076	3.639
26	50	0.872665	0.079	3.432
27	55	0.959931	0.094	3.638
28	60	1.047198	0.107	3.625
29	65	1.134464	0.126	3.602
30	70	1.221730	0.159	3.679
31	75	1.308997	0.206	3.600
32	80	1.396263	0.309	3.623
33	85	1.483530	0.593	3.487
34	5	0.087266	0.060	4.063
35	10	0.174533	0.063	4.182
36	15	0.261799	0.061	3.949
37	20	0.349066	0.065	4.122
38	25	0.436332	0.063	3.844
39	30	0.523599	0.068	3.976
40	35	0.610865	0.070	3.894
41	40	0.698132	0.077	3.969
42	45	0.785398	0.088	4.196
43	50	0.872665	0.095	4.135
44	55	0.959931	0.101	3.895
45	60	1.047198	0.123	4.164
46	65	1.134464	0.143	4.088
47	70	1.221730	0.176	4.065

Index	θ_0 (degrees)	θ_0 (radians)	Force (N)	E (GPa)
48	75	1.308997	0.223	3.903
49	80	1.396263	0.344	4.029
50	85	1.483530	0.661	3.890
51	5	0.087266	0.867	58.268
52	10	0.174533	0.936	62.162
53	15	0.261799	0.901	58.722
54	20	0.349066	0.960	60.841
55	25	0.436332	1.045	63.879
56	30	0.523599	0.999	58.347
57	35	0.610865	1.150	63.533
58	40	0.698132	1.136	58.691
59	45	0.785398	1.335	63.699
60	50	0.872665	1.410	61.134
61	55	0.959931	1.606	62.137
62	60	1.047198	1.784	60.176
63	65	1.134464	2.160	61.598
64	70	1.221730	2.598	59.958
65	75	1.308997	3.600	62.875
66	80	1.396263	5.131	60.119
67	85	1.483530	9.921	58.341
68	5	0.087266	1.014	68.158
69	10	0.174533	0.951	63.185
70	15	0.261799	0.994	64.789
71	20	0.349066	1.019	64.609
72	25	0.436332	1.108	67.779
73	30	0.523599	1.155	67.515
74	35	0.610865	1.164	64.349
75	40	0.698132	1.296	66.970
76	45	0.785398	1.403	66.943
77	50	0.872665	1.515	65.713
78	55	0.959931	1.628	63.017
79	60	1.047198	1.876	63.303
80	65	1.134464	2.297	65.503
81	70	1.221730	2.729	62.971
82	75	1.308997	3.918	68.420
83	80	1.396263	5.482	64.234
84	85	1.483530	10.921	64.224